

Legal Analysis of Rape, Including Spousal Rape: The Nigerian Perspective

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Abstract:

This work provides an overview of the two distinct categories of sexual violence ‘rape’ and ‘spousal rape’. This work examined the complex and intricate issue of rape and spousal rape, analyzing the legal and social contexts in which they exist in Nigeria. In the Nigerian legal system, victims of rape face significant obstacles in obtaining justice, particularly due to the prevailing rule of law which requires corroborating evidence for conviction, even in cases where the victim is a child. Despite exceptions to this rule, its prominence often impedes victims, especially minors, from successfully proving their cases. However recent events in Nigeria have painted a sobering picture where survivors of rape, having spoken out about their ordeal, have instead faced retaliatory defamation lawsuits and even police investigations. This troubling trend has caused concern among activists, who fear that these court battles and reprisals against survivors may deter others from speaking out about their experiences. This research focused on the definition, perpetrators of rape and also the complexities of marital rape in Nigeria. This paper will end with some concluding remark that Nigeria should follow the international trend towards criminalizing marital rape, given the concerning increase in reports of domestic abuse alone.

Keywords: Rape, Law, Victims, Marriage, Corroboration, Punishment, Nigeria.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Rape is an abhorrent violation of an individual's autonomy, bodily integrity, and dignity. It is a heinous crime that continues to be prevalent in many societies, including in the purview of marriage. This research seeks to provide a comprehensive understanding of certain key terms relevant to the discussion of rape, marital rape and the associated theoretical foundations such as consent, victim, perpetrator and historical exemptions. The concept of rape has been a persistent issue throughout human history, with records of its occurrence dating back as far as ancient times¹. Rape is a type of sexual assault usually involving sexual intercourse or other forms of penetration carried out against a person without the person's consent.²

The offence of rape is complete upon penetration.³ Rape was also defined by the Court of Appeal as an unlawful sexual act with a female without her consent⁴. The court also went further to define rape as the unlawful carnal knowledge of a man with a woman, against the will of the woman. Rape is also defined as the act of sexual intercourse committed by a man with a woman who is not his wife and without her consent. Previously, laws such as the criminal and penal code failed to acknowledge that men could also be victims of rape. However, the 2015 enactment marks a significant turning point, as it recognizes that men can be sexually assaulted⁵. This shift in perspective underscores the urgent need for society to acknowledge and address the issue of sexual violence against men.

In Nigeria, the heinous crime of rape carries severe penalties: life imprisonment with or without caning,⁶ and in some cases, a combination of life imprisonment and a fine.⁷ This reflects the severity of the crime and society's contempt for such an unforgivable violation. The term "spousal rape" refers to unhealthy sexual relations between a husband and wife. However, regardless of how it was obtained, such sexual activity is not considered a crime of rape in Nigerian law, nor is it considered unlawful if neither person gave their consent at the time. "Spousal rape" is the term for such harmful sexual activity that is typically committed by a person's legally wedded partner. In order to safeguard conjugal responsibilities and rights consortium, which sexual relations forms a part of, husbands have been granted a marital exemption from the crime of rape in the majority of countries in the world. A spouse has a duty to have a sexual relationship with their partner.⁸

¹ The Holy Bible, King James version Genesis 34:1-4

² Frances Ewherido, "Can a Man Rape." Vanguard, Saturday, January 18, 2020 <https://www.vanguardngr.com> accessed 20/7/2025

³ Criminal Code Act, Section 6, Penal Code Section 282.

⁴ Captain J Jackson Friday Olali v. Nigerian Army [2016] 4 NWLR Pt 1502 @ page 358.

⁵ Violence Against Persons (Prohibition) Act 2015.

⁶ Criminal Code Act, s. 358 Cap C.38 LFN 2004

⁷ Penal Code, s. 283 Cap 53 LFN 2004

⁸ Agu G. A. and Odike A. E., Modern Nigeria Family law and Succession (Nigeria: Vougasen Limited 2003).

2. ANALYSIS OF THE CONCEPT OF RAPE

Throughout this work, certain terms will be consistently used and it is crucial to provide clarity on their meanings. These key terms include rape, consent, victim, perpetrator which are all fundamental in understanding the issue of “rape and marital rape”.

2.1 RAPE

The word “rape” has its roots in the latin term *rapere* (*supine stem raptum*), which means “to seize, to grasp, to take away”. In Roman legal context, the abduction of a woman through force, with or without sexual intercourse, was termed as “*raptus*”⁹ Rape, a criminal act, represents one of the most serious types of sexual assault. It entails any non-consensual sexual intercourse between a man and a girl or woman. Medically, rape is described as the penile penetration of the vulva¹⁰ Rape simply means sexual intercourse with a girl or woman without the consent of the girl or woman¹¹ The legal definition of rape is when someone puts their penis in another person’s vagina, anus or mouth, without the person’s permission¹² However, Rape can be committed against a person who is incapable of giving valid consent, such as one who is unconscious, incapacitated, has an intellectual disability, or is below the legal age of consent. According to the law in the United Kingdom¹³ under section 1 of the Sexual Offences Act (2003), rape is defined as:

A person (A) commits an offence if he intentionally penetrates the vagina, anus or mouth of another person (B) with his penis.

(b) B does not consent to the penetration, and

(c) A does not reasonably believe that B consents. Whether a belief is reasonable is to be determined having regard to all the circumstances, including any steps A has taken to ascertain whether B consents.....

A person guilty of an offence under this section is liable, on conviction on indictment, to imprisonment for life.

According to the United States¹⁴ Department of Justice, rape is defined as:

⁹ Smith, M.D., ed. (2004). Encyclopedia of rape (Westport CT Greenwood Press 2004) p.169

¹⁰ JK Mason and A. M. Smith, Law and Medical Ethics, (London: Butherworths, 1987) 22.

¹¹ Okonkwo and Naishon Criminal law in Nigeria.(2nd edn, Ibadan, Spectrum Books, 1980,) 271

¹² Chiazor I. A., Ozoya M. I., Udume M. 8 Egharevba M. E. Taming the Rape Scourge in Nigeria: Issues and Actions Gender and Behaviour Vol.14 (3) 2016

¹³ A Critical analysis of the UK’s definition of rape shows that the offence can only be committed by a man

¹⁴ An updated definition of rape, available at <http://www.justice.gov/opa/blog/updated-definition-rape>>accessed 24th May, 2024.

Penetration no matter how slight of the vagina or anus with any body part or object, or oral penetration by a sex organ of another person, without the consent of the victim.

By the definition above provided by the Department of Justice, it is evident that the law does not adhere to an immutable pattern. Instead, the law varies across different locations and eras and is subject to ongoing revision and renewal. This dynamic nature of law underscores the necessity of change to ensure that it remains just.

However, the provisions regarding rape are delineated in two major Nigerian statutes, among others, the Criminal code¹⁵ and the Penal code.¹⁶ It is imperative to elucidate that while the criminal code pertains to the southern states of Nigeria, the penal code governs the northern states. This research work will reveal that, despite the divergent definitions of rape within these statutes, the resultant interpretations are fundamentally equivalent. It is also pertinent to observe that neither statute provides an explicit definition of the offence of rape. Rather, they delineate the constituent elements of the offence which happened to be the fact that the prosecution must establish beyond a reasonable doubt to achieve conviction. In this context, section 357 of the criminal code provides that:

Any person who has unlawful carnal knowledge of a woman or girl without her consent, or with her consent, if the consent is obtained by force or by means of threat or intimidation of any kind, or by fear of harm or by means of false and fraudulent representation as to the nature of the act, or in the case of a married woman by personating her husband, is guilty of an offence which is called rape.

Likewise, section 282 of the Penal code provides that:

- (1) A man is said to commit rape who, save where he had sexual intercourse with his wife, has sexual intercourse with a woman in any of the following circumstances:
 - (a) Against her will,
 - (b) Without her consent,
 - (c) With her consent when her consent has been obtained by putting her in fear of death or of harm,
 - (d) With her consent, when the man knows that he

¹⁵ Cap 38, Laws of the Federation of Nigeria, 2004 sections 357 and 358

¹⁶ Cap 89, Laws of Northern Nigeria, 1963, sections 282 and 283.

- (e) is not her husband and that her consent is given because she believes herself to be lawfully married, With or without her consent, when she is under 14 years of age or of unsound mind.
- (2) Sexual Intercourse by a man with his own wife is not rape. If she has obtained puberty.

An important observation to glean from these two primary statutory provisions is the legal incapacity of a woman to perpetrate the offence of rape against a man. This stems from the explicit stipulation within both statutes that rape can exclusively be perpetrated against a woman or girl nonetheless, it warrants acknowledgment that pursuant to section 7 of the Criminal code, although a woman may lack the legal capacity to commit rape, but she remains liable for complicity in the offence through aiding, abetting, counseling or procuring it's commission¹⁷ in essence, these statutes delineate that only a woman or girl can be deemed a victim of rape.

But a recent legislative enactment, known as the Violence Against Persons Prohibition Act 2015 (VAPP), heralds a significant departure from past legal frameworks in Nigeria. Unlike its predecessors, which narrowly captured rape solely within the context of female victims, the VAPP stands out for its revolutionary recognition that men too can fall prey to this heinous crime. Section 1 of the VAPP emphatically underscore this progressive stance as follow.¹⁸

(1) A person commits the offence of rape if:

- a) He or she intentionally penetrates the vagina, or anus or mouth of another person with any other part of his or her body or anything else.
- b) The other person does not consent to the penetration or,
- c) The consent is obtained by force or means of threat or intimidation of any kind or by fear of harm or by means of false and fraudulent representation as to the nature of the act.
- d) Or the use of any substance or additive capable of taking away the will of such person or in the case of a marriage by impersonating his or her spouse.

¹⁷ R v Cogan and Leak [1975] Crim L.R. 584.

¹⁸ Violence Against Persons (Prohibition) Act 2015.

The Act acknowledges that men, akin to women and girls, can be victims of rape. It expands the definition of rape to encompass any non-consensual penetration of a man's anus or mouth, specifying that this can be achieved with various body parts or objects, such as hands, dildos, pens, cucumbers rather than being limited to penile penetration. In other words, the above shows that rape is not just the penetration of the vagina with a penis but includes much more¹⁹

2.2 TYPES OF RAPE

Rape can be categorized in different ways for example by reference to the situation in which it occurs, by the identity or characteristics of the victim, and by the identity or characteristics of the perpetrator.

2.2.1 Statutory rape

Sexual intercourse with a person below the age of consent, i.e the age at which legal competence is established is referred to as statutory rape²⁰. The age at which an individual may give effective consent to sexual intercourse is commonly set in most countries at between 14 and 18 years (although it is as low as 12 years in some other countries). Sexual activity that violates the age of consent law, but is neither violent nor physically coerced is sometime described as “statutory rape”, which is a legally recognized category in Nigeria.

2.2.2 Serial rape

Serial rape is rape committed by a person over a relatively long period of time and committed on a number of victims. Most times, this type of rapist is unknown to the victim and follows a specific and predictable pattern of targeting victims. A serial rapist is someone who commits multiple rapes, whether with multiple victims or a single victim repeatedly over a period of time. Some serial rapists target children.²¹

2.2.3 Date and acquaintance rape

The term, “date rape” is used to refer to several types of rape, broadly acquaintance rape, which is a non-domestic rape committed by someone who knows the victim and Drug Facilitated Sexual Assault (DFSA) where the rapist intentionally drugs the victim with a date rape drug so that they are incapacitated. Acquaintance rape constitutes the vast majority of reported rapes while (DFSA) is infrequent. A frequently overlapping category is incapacitated rape, where the victim is incapacitated and unable to give consent, this is often the result of intoxication, but can also simply be because the victim is asleep or has

¹⁹ J. Karen, *The Legal Response to Violence Against Women* (New York: Garland Publishing Inc.1997) p.16.

²⁰ C. M. Cusack, *Laws Relating to sex, pregnancy, and Infancy: Issues in Criminal Justice* (2015).

²¹ Nardos Rachel, *Overcoming Violence Against Women and Girls* (G.U publishers 2003). P.17.

a medical condition. In a DFSA situation, the rapist intentionally incapacitates the victim via drugs, while acquaintance rape can occur when the victim is not incapacitated.²²

2.2.4 Gang rape

A gang rape, also known as a group rape or multiple perpetrator rape, is a form of sexual assault in which two or more people work together to forcibly rape a victim. The attackers may be known to each other or may be strangers who gang up together to commit the crime. Offenders and victims in gang rape incidents are younger with a higher possibility of being unemployed. Gang rapes involved more alcohol and other drug use, night attacks and severe sexual assault and less victim resistance and fewer weapons than individual rapes²³

2.3 ELEMENTS OF RAPE

In a continuum of judicial pronouncements, the courts in Nigeria have invariably adhered to the legal provisions on rape as delineated in the statutes, specifically the Criminal Code, the Penal code, and more recently, the Violence Against Persons Prohibition Act of 2015. The Courts have affirmed that rape is defined as the act of sexual intercourse perpetrated by a man or woman upon another individual whether man, girl, or woman without the other party's lawful consent.²⁴ In *Posu v The State*,²⁵ the Supreme Court delineated the constituent elements of the offence of rape. The court said that in an indictment for rape or unlawful carnal knowledge of a person without their consent, it is incumbent upon the prosecution to establish the following elements beyond a reasonable doubt:

- (a) That the accused had sexual intercourse with the prosecutrix,
- (b) That the act of sexual intercourse was done without her consent or the consent was obtained by fraud, force, threat, intimidation, deceit or impersonation,
- (c) That the prosecutrix was not the wife of the accused,
- (d) That the accused had the *mens rea*, the intention to have sexual intercourse with the prosecutrix without her consent, or that the accused acted recklessly not caring whether the prosecutrix consented or not.

²² C.A. Gidycz, A Comparison of Group and Individual Sexual Assault Victims [1910] *Psychology of Women Quarterly*, 325-342.

²³ A. H. Miranda "Handbook on the Study of Multiple Perpetrator Rape: A Multi Disciplinary Response to an International Problem (2013), 30 (Routledge Publisher 2014) 10

²⁴ *Okoyomon v The State* [1973] ISC 21; *Mogaji v The Nigerian Army* [2008], 34 NSC QR (pt 1) 108; *Upahar v The State* [2003] 6 NWLR (pt. 816) 23; *Ogunbayo v The State* [2007] 8 NWLR (pt. 1035) 157.

²⁵ [2011] 2 NWLR (pt 1234) 393

It is imperative to recognize that even the slightest penetration suffices to constitute the act of sexual intercourse and whether there was insemination during such penetration is immaterial.²⁶ For the prosecution to substantiate the offence of rape, the prosecutrix must incontrovertibly establish the case beyond reasonable doubt as this responsibility exclusively rests on the prosecution. The prosecution must not only demonstrate that sexual penetration occurred, but also prove that such penetration was without the consent of the victim. Additionally, such rape incident must be reported to law enforcement agency coupled with a medical examination²⁷. To prove rape, the prosecution must show that the accused had sexual intercourse, without the victim's consent.²⁸ In the case of *Rabiu v State*²⁹. The Supreme Court reaffirmed the long-standing principle that the prosecution must adduce credible evidence to substantiate the elements of rape to the court's satisfaction, in order to secure a conviction. Proving guilt beyond reasonable doubt necessitates presenting evidence that is both conclusive and compelling.³⁰

Also, in *Iko v The State*,³¹ the appellant who was a taxi driver, was asked by the prosecutrix's father to take her to school in his cab. On their way to school, it was alleged that the appellant parked his car, wound up the glass, locked the car and over powered the girl by removing her pant and having sexual intercourse with her, after which he drove her to his apartment. At around 9: pm., the girl raised an alarm and reported to the appellant's neighbor where she had to pass the night. Afterwards, she reported the incident to her father who reported to the police. The High Court convicted the appellant or perpetrator. On appeal, the Court of Appeal affirmed the conviction. However, on further appeal to the Supreme Court of Nigeria, the conviction was quashed because the ingredients of rape were not proved.

2.4 PUNISHMENT FOR RAPE

The atrocious crime of rape is punished by several statutes with diverse penalties. According to the criminal code, an individual convicted of rape is liable to life imprisonment.³² Section 358 of the criminal code explicitly mandates as follows: "any person who commits the offence of rape is liable to imprisonment for life with or without canning." Moreover, the Penal code, as a significant statute addressing the crime of rape, imposes stringent penalties by mandating either life imprisonment or a minimum term of three years' incarceration. Section 283 of the penal code provides that notwithstanding

²⁶ *Iko v State* [2000] LPELR – SC. 177/2001.

²⁷ C.T. Emejuru, *An Appraisal of the Jurisprudence of Spousal Rape in Nigeria*.

²⁸ *Ibid*.

²⁹ [2015] 7 NWLR (Pt. 825) 491 @ 508.

³⁰ *Smart v State* [2016] LPELR 40827 (SC)

³¹ [2001] FWLR (pt 68), 1161 to 1196; *Akpanefe v The State* [1969] I ALL NWLR 420

³² Section 358 Criminal Code

the provision of any other law contrary, whoever commits rape shall be punished with imprisonment for life or for such a term not less than three years.³³

However, Section 1 (2) of the Violence Against Persons Prohibition Act 2015 provide that: “a person convicted of an offence under subsection (1) of this section is liable to imprisonment for life except.

- (a) Where the offender is less than 14 years the offender is liable to a maximum of 14 years imprisonments.
- (b) In all other cases to a minimum of 12 years imprisonment without an option of fine.
- (c) In the case of rape by a group of persons, the offenders are liable jointly to a minimum of 20 years imprisonment without an option of fine.”

In numerous recent rulings, the court has utilized these statutes to convict offenders and impose appropriate sentences: In a 2022 decision reported in the dailies, Justice Ita Mbaba of the Court of Appeal, Kano Division³⁴ delivered six judgements on cases on Appeal from the Jigawa State High Court, and imposed life sentences on three convicts. The three appellants were convicted and subsequently sentenced pursuant to the provisions outlined in the penal code (Miscellaneous Amendment) law of 2019 in Jigawa State. This law mandates life imprisonment for individuals found guilty of rape.

Also, a sexual and domestic violence court sitting in Ikeja sentenced a 43-year-old trader, Adelaja Oloyede to 25 years imprisonment for raping a tailor in the Ikorodu area of Lagos state. Justice Abiola Sola Doye found the accused guilty of the charge of rape contrary to section 260 of the Criminal Law of Lagos State³⁵. Ultimately, one of the objectives of this punitive measure is act as a deterrent against future instances of rape, while also serving as a means to deliver justice to the victims who have suffered profound mental, psychological, physical and emotional trauma.

2.5 PENETRATION

The Black Law Dictionary³⁶ defines penetration as “the entry of the penis or some other part of the body or a foreign object into the vagina or other bodily orifice.” Rape is complete as soon as the male organ touches the outer cover of the female organ without

³³ Section 283 Penal Code

³⁴ Dahiru Suleiman, Rapist Jailed for Life in Jigawa ,<www.guardian.ng Three rapist get life sentence in Jigawa>. Accessed on the 25th May, 2024.

³⁵ Ibid Lagos Court sentences trader to 26 years imprisonment for rape. Accessed on the 25th May 2024

³⁶ B. A. Garner, Black’s Law Dictionary (Ninth edn,) p. 1248

her consent³⁷. Mere sexual gratification such as scratching or rubbing of the opening of the vagina with the penis leading to ejaculation will not constitute rape but indecent assault because there was no penetration.³⁸ In *R v. Mayberry*,³⁹ the court held inter alia that the offence is committed upon penetration whether or not there was ejaculation, and that the act of sexual Intercourse which accompanies it is part of the offence, Therefore, where a person gives aid after penetration, the aider is liable as well .

2.6 CONSENT

The Black's Law Dictionary⁴⁰ defined consent as an agreement, approval, or permission as to some act or purpose, especially given voluntarily by a competent person; legally effective assent. Consent is an affirmative defence to assault, battery, and related torts. Consent maybe a defence to a crime if the victim has the capacity to consent and if the consent negates an element of the crime or thwarts the harm that the law seeks to prevent. Consent is a crucial element in the definition of rape as provided in section 357 of the criminal code as follows:

Any person who has unlawful carnal knowledge of a woman or girl without her consent, or with her consent, if the consent is obtained by force or by means of threats or intimidation of any kind, or by fear of harm or by means of false and fraudulent representation as to the nature of the act, or, in the case of a married woman, by personating her husband, is guilty of an offence which is called rape.

The lack of consent is a necessary ingredient that the prosecution must show in order to secure the conviction of the accused.⁴¹ However, with regard to consent in rape cases the court in *Ndeudoh v. State*⁴² held that in a charge of rape, the prosecution must prove that the act was done against her will; without her consent. Genuine consent is devoid of inducement, coercion, deceit, intimidation, or false representation including the impersonation of a spouse. A misconceived notion regarding the complainant's consent, albeit unreasonable, may impugn the perpetrator's intent. This legal principle was elucidated in the House of Lords ruling in *DPP v Morgan*⁴³ where the accused, despite harbouring an unreasonable belief in the woman's consent, was exonerated of rape charges.

³⁷ K. Adegbite; Rape under the Nigerian Law (Princeton Publishing Company, Lagos), 21.

³⁸ Lukcy v State [2016] 13 NWLR (pt. 1528) 28 (SC)

³⁹ [1973] QD R. 211.

⁴⁰ B.A Garner, Supra 28

⁴¹ Ali v state [2021] 12 NWLR (pt. 1787): 159 @ 167.

⁴² [2021] 11 NWLR (pt. 1787) 234@ 237

⁴³ [1975] 2 W. L.R; 913

In the case of *Ahamefule v Imperial Med. Centre*,⁴⁴ the court held that in legal parlance, consent entails an element of volition, indicating that the individual is acting independently and by their own free will. Moreover, the case of *R v Kirk*⁴⁵ illustrates the complexities surrounding the nature of consent. The 14-year old complainant was a helpless and impoverished girl who had sex with the defendant in exchange for cash she could use to purchase food. Despite the fact that there was no overt coercion to get the complainant's agreement, the Court of Appeal maintained the defendant's rape conviction. This ruling unequivocally shows that excessive pressure can come in many forms. It was sufficient to show that the complainant could not freely select and did not consent, given her belief that her circumstances left her with little alternative but to submit to the sexual intercourse.

However, in *R v Watson*,⁴⁶ the court held that where a complainant submits due to a perceived inability to resist, the circumstances might lead to a determination of reluctant agreement and consequently, consent. This verdict appears to be in direct opposition to the ruling in *R v Olugboja*,⁴⁷ wherein it was held that a clear distinction must be made between submission and reluctant acquiescence with the former not constituting consent. The second element intrinsic to the definition of consent concerns the complainant's capacity to provide it. For a complainant to possess sufficient capacity to consent, they must have adequate knowledge to make an informed decision, as articulated in *R v Howard*.⁴⁸ Also, in *R v Cooper*,⁴⁹ the court determined that the pivotal inquiries are firstly, whether the complainant possesses the capability to comprehend the information pertinent to the decision they are required to make and secondly, whether they possess the ability to appraise that information in order to make an informed decision. Consequently, this means that a complainant with a mental disorder who can understand the nature of the act to which they are being asked to consent may still lack the capacity to consent if they are unable to evaluate whether they should agree.

Prior to this ruling, the standard was solely based on whether the complainant could understand the nature of the act; if they could, they were deemed to have the requisite capacity to consent.⁵⁰ In the case of *kaitamaki v The Queen*,⁵¹ the defendant contended that he was under the impression that the victim was consenting at the initiation of

⁴⁴ [2005] 5 NWLR (pt. 917) 57

⁴⁵ [2008] EWCA Crime 434

⁴⁶ [2015] EWCA Crim 559

⁴⁷ [1982] Q.B. 320 CA

⁴⁸ [1965] 50 Cr APP R. 56

⁴⁹ [2009] 1 WLR 1786

⁵⁰ X City Council VMB, NB and MAB [2006] EWHC 168 (Fam)

⁵¹ [1985] A. C. 147

penetration. It was only subsequent to penetration that he became aware of lack of consent, yet he failed to desist. Consequently, he was adjudged capable of rape.

Another circumstance in which capacity may become a pivotal issue involves situations where the complainant is voluntarily intoxicated. In such scenarios, the jury must consider four factors as stated in *R v Coates*.⁵² Intoxication can diminish a complainant's inhibitions, potentially causing them to engage in actions they would not ordinarily undertake while sober. Nonetheless, the fact that a complainant consents while intoxicated does not inherently negate the validity of their consent. The paramount consideration is whether the level of intoxication was sufficient to nullify the complainant's capacity to consent. A complainant may experience this state of incapacitation even while remaining conscious; they might be cognizant of their unwillingness to consent yet unable to articulate it or they may be altogether incapable of making an informed decision. An unconscious complainant categorically cannot provide consent, irrespective of any physiological responses their body might exhibit to the defendant's actions.

However, in regard to consent, it is no excuse that the complainant is a common prostitute or the girlfriend of the accused and has consented to the intercourse on other occasions. In the case of *Utang v State*, where the complainant denied having consensual sex, the appellant, DSP James Utang, failed to convince the court with claims that he gave a jolly ride to the complainant and happily had drinks with her before having consensual sex with her.⁵³

2.7 Submission

The Black's Law Dictionary defines submission as: (1) a yielding, or readiness to yield to the authority or will of another: (2) a contract in which the parties agree to refer their dispute to a third party for resolution.⁵⁴ Submission refers to the act of acquiescing or yielding to a person or situation under pressure or duress. According to Smith and Hogan,⁵⁵ it is doubtful if submission can exculpate the offence of rape as what the law requires is consent and not submission. In criminal law, there is a difference between consent and submission; while consent may defeat a charge of rape, submission cannot produce such an effect.⁵⁶

⁵² [2008] 1 Cr APP. R52

⁵³ *Utang v State* [2021] 16 NWLR (1802) 381.

⁵⁴ B.A. Garner, *Black's Law Dictionary* Ninth edn, pg 1562.

⁵⁵ Smith and Hogan, *Criminal Law*, (8th edn , London, Butterworths) p. 468

⁵⁶ Agent, MaduenyiIhua. "Lecture Notes on Sexual Offences in Nigeria". Department of Commercial and Industrial Law, Faculty of Law, University of Port Harcourt, 2024.

2.8 Victims

A “victim” according to the Black’s Law Dictionary is defined as a person harmed by a crime, tort or other wrong.⁵⁷ A victim refers to the individual who has been subjected to unwanted sexual acts. It is also anyone who has been raped or sexually assaulted, on whom the offence of rape has been committed.⁵⁸

2.9 Perpetrators

A perpetrator is defined by the Black’s Law Dictionary as a person who commits a crime or offence.⁵⁹ A perpetrator refers to the person who carries out the unwanted sexual act against another person without consent. In other words, he is an individual who commits a crime or is responsible for a particular wrongful act. This term is commonly used in legal and criminal contexts to describe someone who has carried out an illegal act, such as theft, assault, or fraud. It can also be used more broadly to refer to anyone who has caused harm or committed an offence against another person or group.

3. MARRIAGE

Marriage is conventionally understood to constitute a union between a man and a woman, necessitating the involvement of partners of opposite sexes. The act of sexual intercourse is deemed an indispensable element of a legitimate marriage, thereby requiring the union to be between a man and a woman.⁶⁰ Although contemporary medical advancements permit individuals to alter their gender through surgical procedures, the Nigerian legal framework recognizes only unions between a man and a woman. Consequently, marriages involving individuals of the same sex are considered to be void. To substantiate the existence of a legitimate marriage, it is imperative to demonstrate that the parties involved are a man and a woman. In the case of *Corbett v Corbett*,⁶¹ the petitioner and respondent underwent a marriage ceremony. The petitioner was cognizant that the respondent had been registered as male at birth and had subsequently undergone a surgical procedure to remove the penis and construct an artificial vagina. Despite the respondent living as a woman post-surgery, the court determined that the respondent remained biologically male, rendering the marriage void.

3.1 Marital rape

There is an inevitable expectation of sexual intercourse or some form of sexual interaction between two competent adults, which in itself, is not deemed illegal or criminal. However, the legality of such acts hinges upon the presence of genuine consent. In the absence of

⁵⁷ B.A Garner, *Supra* 46 at 1703

⁵⁸ J. Herring, *Criminal Law, Text, Cases, and Materials* (6th edn, OUP 2019)

⁵⁹ B.A. Garner, *Supra* 46 at 1256

⁶⁰ E.I.Nwogugu, . *Family Law in Nigeria*. (Ibadan: Heinemann Educational books Nigeria 2001)

⁶¹ [1992] ALL ER 187

legitimate consent,⁶² such actions are deemed criminal and are categorized as rape according to legal statutes. According to the Black's Law Dictionary,⁶³ marital rape is defined as a husband's sexual intercourse with his wife by force or without her consent. This definition is problematic as it implies that only wives can be victims, possibly influenced by antiquated notions that men cannot be subjected to rape. The concept of spousal rape, also known as marital rape, is delineated in numerous jurisdictions as a circumstance wherein one spouse engages in sexual intercourse without the explicit consent of the other. This form of sexual transgression entails nonconsensual copulation perpetrated by a spouse, frequently utilizing coercion, threats or intimidation to enforce compliance. Such sexual encounters may encompass acts of anal, virginal, or oral intercourse.⁶⁴

In addition, in numerous societies, the right to sexual intimacy within marriage has traditionally been construed as an integral facet of the conjugal rights and obligations between spouses, with its deprivation potentially serving as a ground for divorce.⁶⁵ The concept of spousal rape was previously deemed implausible, as legally wedded partners were regarded as incapable of perpetrating such an offence against each other. However, with regard to marital rape in Nigerian context, one glaring indication of the inadequacy and outdated nature of current criminal law lies in its failure to recognize spousal rape as a criminal offence. Presently, Nigerian law does not acknowledge marital rape, and consequently, it is not addressed in the legal codes, reflecting the belief that a husband cannot rape his wife. Section 282 (2) of the Penal Code Act exemplifies this stance by stating that sexual intercourse between a man and his wife is not considered rape unless the wife has not reached puberty.⁶⁶

Essentially, this statutory definition implies that sexual intercourse without the woman's consent is only classified as rape if the individuals involved are not married; if they are married, the husband cannot be charged with rape. Both the Penal Code Act in Northern Nigeria and the Criminal Code Act in southern Nigeria affirm this position, stating unequivocally that a husband cannot be prosecuted for raping his wife under any circumstances.

⁶² 357 Criminal Code Act 1990 s.357

⁶³ B. A. Garner, *Black's law Dictionary* (10th edn, Thomson West, 2014)

⁶⁴ Violence Against Persons Prohibition Act, 2015 s.1

⁶⁵ Matrimonial Causes Act 1990 s. 15(1)

4. NATIONAL LEGAL FRAMEWORK

4.1 The Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria, 1999 (as Amended)

The Constitution is the grundnorm and Chapter IV deals extensively with fundamental rights. By section 34(1),⁶⁷ every individual is entitled to respect for the dignity of his person, and accordingly, no person shall be subjected to torture or inhumane or degrading treatment. This provision shows that the constitution guarantees the right to dignity and therefore one must not suffer inhuman or degrading treatment. It is submitted that the act of rape inflicts breaches this provision. Exempting rape in marriage goes against this provision of the constitution.

4.2 The Criminal Code Act, (2004)

The Criminal Code Act is a significant legislation in Nigeria's legal system. It defines the offence of rape but it did not include spousal rape as an offence, instead exempting spouses from prosecution for raping their partners.

The Criminal code Act section 357 provides as follows:

Any person who has unlawful carnal knowledge of a woman or girl, without her consent, or with her consent, if the consent is obtained by force or by means of threats or intimidation of any kind, or by fear of harm, or by means of false and fraudulent representation as to the nature of the act, or in the case of a married woman, by personating her husband, is guilty of an offence which is called Rape.⁶⁸

Also, section 6 of the Criminal Code Act provides that:

When the term 'carnal knowledge or the term 'carnal connection' is used in defining an offence, it is implied that the offence, so far as regards that element of it, is complete upon penetration 'unlawful carnal knowledge' means carnal connection which takes place otherwise than between husband and wife.

However, given that "unlawful carnal knowledge" in the legal context refers to sexual intercourse outside of marriage, as defined by section 357 of the Criminal code, it is implied that sexual relations between spouses are considered lawful and cannot be classified as rape, even in cases where consent is lacking or obtained through force or

⁶⁷ Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria 1999 as (Amended), S.34(1)

⁶⁸ The Criminal Code, S. 357

deception. This interpretation stems from the notion that such relations are a fulfillment of conjugal rights. Thus, the criminal code does criminalize spousal sexual intercourse, effectively granting marital exemption from rape charges. It is worth noting that this exemption is broader under the criminal code compared to the penal code,⁶⁹ as the latter considers sexual intercourse with a spouse who has not reached puberty as rape. This distinction underscores the full existence of the spousal rape exemption under the Criminal code.

4.3 The Penal Code Act, 2004

The penal code stands as another pivotal statute, delineating the offence of rape while currently affording spouses a marital rape exemption. Under section 282 (1) of the penal code provides the circumstances under which a man can commit rape upon a woman, that is if he has sexual intercourse with a female in any of the following circumstances:

- (a) Against her will
- (b) Without her consent
- (c) With her consent when her consent has been obtained by putting her in fear of death or of hurt:
- (d) With her consent when the man knows that he is not her husband and that her consent is given because she believes that he is another man to whom she believes herself to be lawfully married:
- (e) With or without her consent if she is under fourteen years of age or of unsound mind
- (2) Sexual intercourse by a man with his own wife is not rape if she has attained puberty.

The pivotal limb of *section 282*, germane to this research endeavor, pertains to its subsection 2 within the penal code. This subsection serves as a caveat to the provisions delineated in subsections (1) (a) -(e) of section 282. Essentially, any sexual encounter falling under the preview of subsection 2 is exempted from the classification of rape. This statutory provision establishes a spousal rape exemption, absolving a spouse from criminal culpability for engaging in sexual intercourse with their partners, even under coercive circumstances.

However, this exemption hinges upon the condition that the spouse in question has attained puberty. Further scrutiny reveals that section 282 (2) of the Penal code harbors certain exemptions. Specifically, it stipulates that sexual intercourse by a man with her wife is not deemed rape if she has reached puberty. Implicitly, this exemption does not extend to a spouse partaking in sexual activity with a partner who has not yet attained

⁶⁹ The Penal code, S.282(2)

puberty. Consequently, this statutory provision shields a spouse who engages in sexual intercourse, irrespective of the circumstances with another spouse who has attained puberty. By virtue of the wording and logical deduction derived from section 282 (2), it suggests that a man could indeed face charges of rape if the spouse involved has not reached puberty. It is paramount to note that section 282 (2) of the penal code not provide an absolute indemnity for spousal sexual relations. In instances where forceful sexual activity occurs between spouses, and one spouses has not attained puberty, this perpetrator is criminally liable for rape. This contrasts with the Criminal code Act, which offers an unconditional exemption for forceful, non-consensual sexual intercourse between spouses.

4.4 Child Rights Act, 2003

The Child Rights Act (CRA) is a federal legislative enactment crafted to safeguard the rights of children. This law has also been passed by several states in Nigeria. Section 31(1) & (2) of the CRA⁷⁰ unequivocally establishes that engaging in sexual intercourse with a child constitutes the grave offence of rape, carrying the severe penalty of life imprisonment upon conviction. Furthermore, the CRA underscores that it remains inconsequential whether (a) the perpetrator harbored the belief that the child was of or above the age of eighteen years or, (b) the sexual encounter purportedly occurred with the child's consent. Significantly, the CRA transcends gender boundaries, recognizing that victims of rape can be of any gender, while also acknowledging that perpetrators of this abhorrent crime can be of either gender.

4.5 Matrimonial Causes Act

The Matrimonial Causes Act holds pivotal importance in this research, as it serves as the cornerstone for determining the grounds upon which a spouse may seek exemption from spousal rape allegations, contingent upon the validity of their marriage. Section 15(1) of the Matrimonial Causes Act provides that:

A petition under this Act by party to a marriage for a decree of dissolution of may be presented to the court by either party to the marriage upon the ground that the marriage has broken down irretrievably
(1) The Court hearing a petition for a decree of dissolution of a marriage shall hold the marriage to have broken down irretrievably if, but only if, the petitioner satisfies the court of one or more after following facts.

⁷⁰ Child Right's Act, 2003, S. 1& 2

- (a) The respondent has willfully and persistently refused to consummate the marriage.

The import of this statutory provision is profound, as it acknowledges the importance of consummation of the marital union. This connotes that there ought to be an unbroken sequence of sexual relations between both partners, not merely an isolated occurrence but a persistent practice spanning the entirety of the marriage. Such consummation is deemed a fundamental entitlement of each spouse and a reciprocal duty owed to one another. Thus, any coercive sexual conduct perpetrated by one spouse upon the other would not be construed as rape within this framework. Failure to maintain this continuous consummation may even serve as grounds for the dissolution of the marital bond.⁷¹

4.6 Violence Against Persons Prohibition Act (VAPP), 2015

This legislation marks a departure from preceding statutes that overlooked men as viable victims of rape, especially within marital contexts. While the criminal code narrowly defined rape in terms of vaginal penetration, the VAPP Act expands this definition to encompass any form of penetration whether of the mouth, anus, or vagina perpetrated by another individual. Such acts may involve the use of hands as a variety of objects, including candles, dildos, cucumbers and similar items.

Section (1) The Violence Against Person (Prohibition) Act, 2015 provides that:

A person commits the offence of rape if

- a) He or she intentionally penetrates the vagina, anus or mouth of another person with any other part of his body or her body or anything else;
- b) The other person does not consent to the penetration; or
- c) The consent is obtained by force or means of threat or intimidation of any kind or by fear of harm or by means of false and fraudulent representation as to the nature of the act or the use of any substance or additive capable of taking away the will of such person or in the case of a married person by impersonating his or her spouse.⁷²

The enactment of the Violence Against Persons Prohibition Act, commonly denoted as the VAPP Act, on May 25, 2015, signifies a paradigm shift from previous legal frameworks, heralding an era of expanded conceptualization of rape. Section 1 of the VAPP Act heralds

⁷¹ Matrimonial Causes Act 1990, S.15 (2)

⁷² Violence Against Persons (Prohibition) Act S. 1

a revolutionary redefinition of rape, wherein it encompasses any deliberate utilization of a part of one's body or an external object to penetrate the vaginal, anal or oral orifices of another individual without their explicit consent. Furthermore, it clearly states that in cases where consent was obtained through force or deceptive ways, such acts still constitute rape. This approach can be contrasted with the previous narrow interpretations of rape, which limited it to non-consensual penile – vaginal penetration.

Section 1 (2) of the VAPP Act accentuates the gravity of this offence by imposing the most severe punitive measure available within the purview of the law: a sentence of life imprisonment for convicted rapists. The transformative ramifications of the VAPP Act are readily discernible, elucidating Nigeria's legal system's profound transformations in relation to rape. It robustly acknowledges any form of non-consensual penetration, be it vaginal, anal or oral, perpetrated through bodily appendages or inanimate objects such as sticks, dildos, or carrots, as constituting rape.

This legislative benchmark thus imposes substantially harsher penalties compared to the provisions of the criminal code and penal code. Save for limited exceptions pertaining to minors below the age of 14, the statutory minimum custodial sentence for rape under the VAPP Act is mandatorily stipulated at 12 years imprisonment.

Furthermore, under the section (1) of the VAPP Act, any instance wherein a female perpetrator inserts an object into the anal cavity of a male counterpart during a social liaison without his explicit consent constitutes the offence of anal rape. The offence is punishable with a term of imprisonment not less than 12 years.⁷³

The VAPP Act brings about five significant changes to the offence of rape namely:

- a) Rape can happen to both women and men. In conventional and previous laws concerning rape, men were not recognized as potential victims of the crime. Prior to the enactment of this legislation, only women were considered susceptible to rape. This Act marks the first legislative acknowledgement that men can also be victims of rape.⁷⁴
- b) Formally, rape was associated solely with the use of the penis as the instrument. However, with the inception of this Act, the definition expands the means of commission of the offence to include various other body parts or objects such as cucumbers, carrots, sticks, dildos, pens and the like. ⁷⁵
- c) In earlier statutes like the criminal code, the law stipulated the maximum penalty for rape, granting judges the discretion to impose a jail term lower than the

⁷³ Ibid, s. 3

⁷⁴ Ibid, s. 1

⁷⁵ Ibid, s. 1 (1)

maximum. However, this recent legislation mandates a minimum penalty of 12 years imprisonment for rape.⁷⁶

- d) Regarding financial restitution for victims, the VAPP acknowledges the entitlement of rape victims to receive compensation. This financial support can assist victims in seeking therapy to address the psychological impact of the rape.⁷⁷
- e) Under the provisions regarding the sex offender's register, this recent legislation mandates that individuals convicted of rape have their information recorded in the register. This register serves as a mechanism for government authorities to monitor the whereabouts and activities of sex offenders, including those who have served their sentences. The National Agency for Prohibition of Trafficking in Persons (NAPTIP) has created a database called the (Nigerian Sexual Offenders Database).⁷⁸

5. FACTORS THAT MAY LEAD TO RAPE

Several factors contribute to the increasing number of rape cases in Nigeria. By indigenous cultural standards, the decadence in fashion and dress sense in the Nigerian society today was copied from western countries. Many Nigerian women whether in universities, on the streets, on social media, prefer to dress indecently. This has also contributed immensely to the high rate of rape cases in Nigeria. Even though it cannot be seen as justification for rape, studies have shown that indecent dressing amongst other factors contribute to the spread of rape in Nigeria.⁷⁹

It is true that most causes of rape in Nigeria are possible due to problems with alcohol and drugs. Unemployed youths try to find succor in alcohol and drugs. This situation leads to an increase of violence among youths⁸⁰. Report also has it that adolescents are naturally less in control of their emotions and the use of alcohol may worsen the situation by reducing their ability to make rational decisions, hence such alcohol and drug abuse increase adolescents risk taking behaviors especially with regards to their sexuality.⁸¹

Psychological disorders or imbalances can influence some men's thinking and inter personal behavior, which may contribute to deviant and abhorrent behaviors such as the

⁷⁶ Ibid,s.1 (2)

⁷⁷ Ibid, s.1 (3)

⁷⁸ Ibid,s.1 (4)

⁷⁹ Akinade, E.A., & Sulaiman, A.A. (2010). Socio-Legal Factors that influence the Perpetuation of rape in Nigeria

⁸⁰ Graham et al. and Mumford et al., Social Psychological and Forensic Perspective on Sexual Abuse (IGI Global 2011,2014), accessed 2 May 2024, <https://www.igi-global.com/doi:104018/978-1-5225-3958-zchoo4>.

⁸¹ N. Evelyn Nwagu, "Alcohol and Drug Usage and Adolescents Sexual Behavior in Nigeria" (2016) 31 (2) Health Promotion International 405-413

sexual violation of infants and children, including incestuous acts by fathers against their own daughters. These problems also affect their ways of relating with others.⁸²

In marriage situations, especially after disagreement spouses, the man may want to assert his superiority in the relationship by forcing himself upon the woman. In an attempt to dominate his wife, he will use the ultimate weapon in his arsenal to demean and degrade her. This may be done by forcing sexual relations with her despite her resistance. In this manner, he shows his dominance over her and violates her privacy.⁸³

6. CHALLENGES IN REGULATING RAPE

The Nigerian legal system has come under fire for its apparent shortcomings in providing justice for victims of rape. Amidst the harrowing experiences faced by survivors, ranging from stigma to retaliation, obtaining justice appears to be a daunting, task fraught with challenges. This complex issue is further exacerbated by factors, such as legal hurdles, financial constraints and so on.

6.1 The legal hurdles

In the Nigerian legal system, victims of rape face significant obstacles in obtaining justice, particularly due to the prevailing rule of law which requires corroborating evidence for conviction, even in cases where the victim is a child. Despite exceptions to this rule, its prominence often impedes victims, especially minors, from successfully proving their cases. This strict corroboration requirement can thus be seen as an insurmountable hurdle for victims seeking justice, particularly given the challenges in obtaining corroborative evidence for rape case.

However recent events in Nigeria have painted a sobering picture where survivors of rape, having spoken out about their ordeal, have instead faced retaliatory defamation lawsuits and even police investigations. This troubling trend has caused concern among activists, who fear that these court battles and reprisals against survivors may deter others from speaking out about their experiences. Following Busola Dakolo's accusations of rape against a popular Nigerian pastor Biodun Fatoyinbo, a battle of narratives quickly ensued on social media pitting accusers and advocates against Fatoyinbo's defenders. Amid the clash, Dakolo filled a lawsuit seeking an apology from the pastor, only to have his legal team counter with a defamation suit. The court ordered Dakolo to pay Fatoyinbo one

⁸² J.M. Oluwaleye and I.O Adefioye, "Interrogation of Causes, Effects, and Societal Response to Rape and Child Defilement in Nigeria" (2021) 3 (2) *Interdisciplinary Journal of Rural Community Studies* 11-22, accessed 2 May 2024, <https://duo.org/1051-986/ijrres-2021.vol.3.02.02>

⁸³ T. Luster, "Sexual Abuse History and Problems in Adolescents" (1997) *Journal of Marriage and Family* 145.

million naira in damages, dealing a significant blow to the pursuit of justice for rape survivors.⁸⁴

6.2 Financial constraints

Victims of rape who choose to pursue justice through the Nigerian legal system often face daunting financial hurdles. The cost of litigation can be prohibitively expensive, particularly as the accused can appeal to the Supreme Court, extending the legal battle over a number of years. As a result, many victims are forced to rely on the state to prosecute on their behalf. However, this reliance comes with its own pitfalls, as the state prosecutors may lack the motivation or expertise to vigorously pursue the case, leading to a frustrating and often futile outcome for the victim.

7. ERADICATING RAPE FROM SOCIETY

Rape, a crime that preys upon the vulnerable and robs them of their dignity, is a stain on the fabric of Nigerian society. To free the society from its corrosive clutches, we must embark on a multifaceted campaign of public enlightenment, education, institutional reform and among other things. However, to eradicate the menace of rape in Nigeria, the causes of the menace need to be examined because there may be a danger in neglecting the causes as only the root causes can clearly point out the way towards lasting solutions. Below are some of the solutions to the increasing cases of rape in Nigeria.

7.1 Public enlightenment

Public enlightenment has been shown to be a critical tool in changing behaviour, attitude, beliefs and value system of people. To deconstruct the pervasive myths about sexual assault that permeate our society, a concerted effort of public enlightenment and education must be undertaken. This should involve targeting diverse venues, such as schools, social clubs, cultural gatherings, religious institutions, and media outlets, to reach a wide spectrum of audiences. Only by challenging and debunking these deeply entrenched misconceptions can society hope to reshape our collective understanding of sexual assault, and pave the way for a society that prioritizes empathy, awareness and prevention. Details of these myths are the subject of a well-researched publication⁸⁵

7.2 Education

The Universal Basic Education (UBE) program, implemented by the Nigerian federal government through legislation, was established to ensure that primary and junior

⁸⁴ <https://www.google.com/amp/s/www.bbc.com/news/world-africa-49234844> [Accessed on 25 May, 2024]

⁸⁵ H. Macdonald, *Sexual Assault: A Resource Book for Students* (Vanderstadt Printers 1993); M. Ojo and D. Olufemi, "Assessment of the Acceptance of Rape Myths Among Nigerian University Students: Crawford University in Nigeria Under Survey" (2013) 1 (4) PSBR 98-104

secondary education is free and mandatory for all children in the country⁸⁶. It has been shown that the education of children, especially the girl child, goes a long way in boosting the socio-economic and socio-cultural status of women in the society in the long run. Ensuring gender parity in education through the UBE program will empower women, who have historically been at a disadvantage due to the prioritization of boys' education in developing countries. The combination of gender inequality, poverty and ignorance has fueled a dangerous trend in some parts in Nigeria, where children instead of attending school, are used for street vending by their caregivers. This exposes them to increased risks of sexual exploitation, abuse and trafficking, providing equal and free education for all children will not only enhance their prospects for the future but also serve as a powerful deterrent against sexual assault and exploitation.

7.3 Institutional reform

Preventing sexual assault is an elusive goal without a comprehensive institutional framework that effectively deals with actual cases of sexual assault. This framework involves a cohesive network of functional, skilled, and synchronized services, including the criminal justice system, the police, and social services, all working together to support victims or survivors and bring perpetrators to justice. Providing easily accessible, community-based support services for victims and ensuring successful prosecution of offenders can not only provide justice and healing for victims, but also act as a deterrent and reduce the likelihood of future incidents. Scott, Waler and Gilmore noted that through speaking out, sexual assault victims risked breaking the silence around sexual assault and in this way, gained a voice. Due to the strength and courage of these women, we are witnessing the establishment of services nationwide which support sexual assault victims, increasing understanding of the crime of sexual assault and perhaps, the beginning of a change in society's attitude.⁸⁷

8. CONCLUSION

In conclusion it has been previously asserted that rape is an offence that disproportionately impacts women, perpetuating a gender-based power imbalance. Thus, it is incumbent upon the lawmakers to revise existing laws to recognize the possibility of a male victim being raped by a female perpetrator, the growing body of evidence from advanced countries affirms the need for laws that afford equal protection and support to all victims of sexual violence, regardless of gender.

⁸⁶ Roa Aluede, "Universal Basic Education in Nigeria: Matters Arising" (2006) 20(2) *Journal of Human Ecology* 97-101

⁸⁷ D. Scott, L. Walker, and K. Gilmore, *Breaking the Silence: A Guide to Supporting Adult Victims/Survivors of Sexual Assault*, 2nd edn (Melbourne: CASA House, 1995).

Also, the current legal framework for sexual offences in Nigeria overlooks and fails to adequately, address the issue of marital rape, which is recognized as a form of sexual violence in various other jurisdictions. The underlying concept of “unlawful carnal knowledge” in section 6 of the Criminal Code precludes the possibility of rape within marriage, effectively shielding married individuals from prosecution for non-consensual sexual acts against their spouses. This omission in the legal framework results in a critical lacuna that leaves victims of marital rape without legal recourse and perpetuates the societal perception that spousal rape is not a crime. This paper recommends the reform of sections 6 and 357 of the criminal code and section 282 of the penal code to balance spousal rights with health concerns in sexual relations. Furthermore, to reflect contemporary issues and tackle rape-related challenges in 21st century Nigeria, the Criminal and Penal Codes should be amended, taking a gender-neutral approach recognizing marital rape, and expanding the legal definition of rape to include objects.